

ROLE OF DARK TRIAD PERSONALITY TRAITS (PSYCHOPATHY, NARCISSISM, AND MACHIAVELLIANISM) IN JOB CRAFTING AMONG WORKING ADULTS

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Abstract

This quantitative study examines the connection between job crafting and the Dark Triad personality traits of psychopathy, narcissism, and Machiavellianism among Pakistani working people. A sample of 300 participants from various organizational sectors participated in a cross-sectional survey design. The findings demonstrated that Machiavellianism emerged as a key predictor of job crafting. Narcissism and psychopathy do not have influence over job crafting. The study also discovered that there were no gender differences in Dark Triad personality traits but differences across genders in job crafting were found significant. This study emphasizes the significance of taking cultural quirks into account when analyzing organizational behavior and advances our knowledge of the Dark Triad personality traits in a non-Western cultural setting. The results offer insights on the hiring, screening, and training of staff members with Dark Triad personality traits, which can be useful for clinicians, organizations, and human resource professionals. Clinicians can create more effective interventions to help these personality's professional and personal development, and organizations can use these individuals' strengths and distinctive qualities to improve outcomes. The discussion of limitations and future directions emphasizes the necessity of experimental and longitudinal research to better understand the connections between Dark Triad personality traits and work outcomes like job crafting, performance, turnover rates, and many other areas.

INTRODUCTION

Abundance of literature is provided upon how favorable attitudes at work are linked to advantageous organizational outcomes like reduced rates of turnover, enhanced collaboration and better job performance, it is crucial for organizations to have positive work attitudes among their employees (Kozlowski, 2012). But not every employee possesses a positive personality trait. Employees who possess

positive personality traits show better performance at work as explained by previous research. Greater levels of transparency have a major impact on leadership effectiveness. Because of their comprehension and innovative thinking, people with these positive qualities (PT) can assume leadership roles within the team (Zhang et al., 2019). The findings of one of the studies indicate that while conscientiousness is an

important indicator of contextual performance, it is not a direct predictor of employee well-being, including psychological distress and job satisfaction (Miller et al., 1999). However, regarding the dark trio of personality traits (psychopathy, Machiavellianism, and narcissism), it is less known that it affects the workplace performance of leaders, subordinates and environment as well. The study of personality's shadow side or dark side is still in its infancy (Jonason, 2022). Until recently, psychological research has focused on negative qualities, such as narcissism, which is referred to as narcissistic personality disorder. The "light" side of personality, which is evaluated, for instance, by the Five Factor Model, or "Big Five" (Terracciano & McCrae, 2006) and its prevalence in both research and practice around personality psychology, may be partly responsible for the delayed rise of Dark Triad research. Even so, "dark" or shadow side of personality can provide even more insight into personality traits and behavioral styles than the Big Five can. According to Levy et al. (2011), The following are the personality qualities that make up the "dark triad": (1) narcissism, which is marked by conceit and high self-esteem; (2) psychopathy, constituted by phenotypic dimensions such as a lack of inhibition arrogance, and courage, together with a lack of empathy and sorrow; and (3) Machiavellianism, is defined by a tendency to take advantage of and manipulate other people in order to further one's own goals (Jones and Paulhus, 2009). According to the hypothesis of the Dark Triad put forth by Paulhus and Williams (2002), Along with social intelligence, a collection of non-pathological traits of personality, or non-pathological characteristics, have an impact on social behavior. Numerous scholars believe that these characteristics together make up the Dark Core of personality, also known as the D-factor (Moshagen et al., 2018). This idea is comparable to the Dark Aspect of Personality. "According to Moshagen et al. (2018), the D-factor is " the propensity to maximize one's personal utility while ignoring, condoning, or maliciously inciting others' disutility, coupled with beliefs that act as excuses. "The term "dark traits" refers to expressions of a basic, dispositional behavioral tendency, which is the Dark Factor of Personality.

Numerous research studies on the dark personality suggest that there has been a surge in interest in the

organizational sciences recently regarding dark personality qualities. Nevertheless, these detrimental aspects of personality are still largely unstudied and misinterpreted. Although there is a correlation between psychopathy, narcissism, and Machiavellianism and a decrease in morals, agreeableness, integrity and humility, and interpersonal emotions (Hodson et al., 2018), and in organizational settings there has been a positive relationship between dark triad personality traits and counter productive work behaviors, manipulation, and power drive (Jonason et al. (2012). However, there's some variations among the three attributes. In this research the relationship between these dark triad personality traits and job crafting has been a focus.

Hypotheses

1. Narcissism is a significant predictor of task crafting and cognitive crafting among working adults.
2. Narcissism is not a significant predictor of relational crafting among working adults.
3. Machiavellianism is a significant predictor of task crafting and cognitive crafting among working adults.
4. Machiavellianism is not a significant predictor of relational crafting among working adults.
5. Psychopathy is not a significant predictor of task crafting, cognitive crafting and relational crafting among working adults.
6. Narcissism and Machiavellianism are significant predictors of job crafting among working adults.
7. Working adults' males perform better in job crafting than working adults' females.

Job crafting

Compared to a century ago, a lot has changed in the design of our current work. Adapting employees to the tasks assigned to them in manufacturing economies was the main goal of early job design. Frederick Taylor established scientific management, an early kind of top-down management, around the beginning of the 20th century. Taylor (1911) proposed several ideas to enhance job crafting, including task simplification, task selection for certain personnel, and task planning and execution distinguish from one another. However, in the ever-evolving modern workplace, managers have labelled these concepts antiquated, finding them ineffective or even destructive at times (Bernoux, 2002). Employees

these days are expected to be proactive in changing their responsibilities and to exercise adaptability. Job crafting is an example of employee activity that has recently been identified as something that companies should encourage to improve working conditions for their employees. A particular type of proactive activity known as "job crafting" occurs when an employee takes the initiative to modify the demands and resources of their work to make their own work more fulfilling, interesting, and meaningful.

When workers willingly alter the tasks, they are given or the characteristics of those jobs, they're doing job crafting (Grant & Parker, 2009; Parker & Ohly 2008; Wrzesniewski & Dutton 2001). Though this construct received a lot of attention, the reasons for such behavior have not been thoroughly studied. For instance, Wrzesniewski and Dutton (2001) identified three different demands that a person can have before beginning to construct a work. Preventing harm to oneself would be the primary necessity. The second is the necessity of communicating a more optimistic view of oneself at work. Satisfying the desire for interpersonal relationships with others was defined as the third need. All of them are primarily self-serving justifications for job crafting. A further strategic benefit of job crafting, as highlighted by Petrou, Demerouti, Schaufeli, and Hetland (2012), is that it can benefit the organization rather than simply the individual in the face of the ongoing organizational change that characterizes many modern post-industrial professions. To do this, the resource pool is optimized through job crafting while maintaining an ideal degree of pressure. Organizational change can be made into an enjoyable experience by carefully structuring the jobs (Avey, Wernsing & Luthans, 2008). The goal of work constructing behavior, according to Wrzesniewski and Dutton (2001), is to change one or more parts of a job to discover meaning. By altering the physical, cognitive, or relational boundaries of a job, these modifications may impact on the entire job or certain aspects of it. The JD-R approach on job crafting places special emphasis on job attributes that can affect workers' motivation and well-being (Petrou et al., 2012; Tims & Bakker, 2010).

It is noteworthy that the JD-R perspective on job crafting is associated with the viewpoint of Wrzesniewski and Dutton (2001). Task crafting,

which may be understood as shifting job needs with relation to the JD-R perspective, involves changing the type or quantity of activities. One way to think of relational crafting is as a shift in job resources. Since shifting the bounds of cognitive tasks is more introspective and presumably not possible on a regular basis, it is more difficult to reframe. Furthermore, attempts to change one's employment are usually captured by task and relational crafting, in contrast to cognitive crafting, which demonstrates participation in a cognitive process of task redefinition. This is like job crafting from the JD-R perspective.

According to Oldham and Hackman (2010), job crafting may have dysfunctional effects since it may generate work process disruptions because of task changes. Those who are prone to ignore the needs of others may also (miss)use job crafting for the following reasons: First, job crafting does not always result in increased organizational effectiveness because it is frequently focused on personal demands (Tims et al., 2012).

Studies have indicated that individuals with higher scores for the dark triad personality traits—narcissism, machismo, and psychopathy— frequently employ deceit to accomplish their objectives at work, irrespective of the impact on other individuals or the business (Jonason et al., 2012). Second, in certain situations, whatever is referred to as "manipulation strategies" may be "job crafting." However, not all job crafting should be seen as deceptive. It is generally accepted that altering your job list to better support the objective of the organization is well-intentioned and not manipulative. This demonstrates the necessity of differentiating between various job crafting types. The impact of dark triad characteristics on job crafting hasn't been studied much up until now. Neale (2019) attempted to reframe the concept of job making by distinguishing between several sorts of job crafting based on intentionality and motivation. Job crafting can also be done by people for selfish or abnormal reasons. Here, we distinguish between work crafting that is done with malice (dark job crafting) and job crafting that is done with good intentions (bright job crafting) (Neale, 2019).

This method of dealing with job crafting seems like a viable tactic to identify unfavorable work outcomes that may be enabled by job crafting. Nonetheless,

Neale's validation of distinguishing between bright and dark task crafting based on intentionality is inadequately defined, both conceptually and operationally. First, since people frequently disagree about what constitutes "deviant" and "well-intentioned" behavior, adding the terms "well-intentioned" and "deviant" to a definition for bright work crafting and dark job constructing puts a subjective aspect into the mix. For instance, someone may view taking on more responsibility than their peers as being well-intentioned for the organization, while others may perceive this as dishonesty since the person is assuming more enjoyable and less taxing work. Second, it seems that the terms "Deviant" and "self-centered" have additionally many different connotations when grouped together within the general umbrella "dark job crafting," even though they are not mutually exclusive. This is primarily since thinking selfishly is not always abnormal. For instance, attempting to do the duties that best suit you may also benefit the organization because it may boost your person-job fitness and enhance your performance (Leana, Appelbaum & Schevuz, 2009). According to a study by Schouten (2022), dark triad types that are happy and involved in their work have a special habit known as "bright job crafting". Furthermore, dark job crafting appears to be a distinct pastime for dark triad People who are not happy with their jobs. Remarkably, when investigating ineffective work habits, this wasn't the case.

According to research, individuals with higher scores on the dark triad of personality traits—Narcissism, Machiavellianism, and Psychopathy—are more likely to employ manipulation techniques to achieve their

goals at work, regardless of the potential negative effects on other individuals or the company (Jonason et al., 2012). So, what one calls is job crafting, others might call it manipulation. There is currently a dearth of research on the connection between personalities and job crafting especially dark triad personalities. This research attempts to identify all these gaps and hopes to fill them by delving into fresh data or discoveries that will benefit the domains of business and psychology.

Materials and methods

The study's non-probability convenient sample consists of 300 working people from Islamabad's public and private sectors. Banks and other financial organizations, business sectors, and service industries are types of organizations from where the data is collected. Both males and females are a part of study. Their educational background ranges from matriculation to PhDs. Participants had to have been employed for at least a year to guarantee that they had had the chance to perform well in their positions, have a sufficient command of English. This criterion was set in accordance with the inclusion criteria of a research done by Geldenhuys, Bakker and Demerouti (2021).

Measures

Demographics

A thorough demographic sheet was created after a variety of demographics were observed to gather data. Demographics included detailed information about the participant's gender, age, marital status, education, and work experience.

Table 1: Frequencies and percentages of the demographic variables of the study (N=300)

Variable	f	%
Gender		
Male	183	39
Female	117	61
Education		
FSC	28	9.3
Graduate	162	54
Masters	107	35.6
PhD	3	1
Employment experience		
1 to 3 years	121	40.3
4 to 6 years	67	22.3

7 to 9 years	28	9.3
Above 10 years	84	28
Marital Status		
Single	144	48
Married	154	51.3
Divorced	3	1
Illness		
Yes	11	3.6
No	289	96.3
Age	Mean=30.14	SD=7.54

Note: f= frequency, %= Percentage

Dark triad personality traits

The Dirty Dozen, a measure of the Dark Triad (narcissism, psychopathy, and Machiavellianism; Paulhus & Williams, 2002), a 12-item scale, was proposed by Jonason and Webster (2010). Each of the three qualities is measured briefly using four items for each dimension. To rate each scale, add the corresponding elements on an ordinal 7-point scale (strongly disagree = 1, strongly agree = 7). The Machiavellianism, Psychopathy, and Narcissism subscales had mean item-level temporal reliability of .92, .84, and .92, respectively.

Job crafting

The job crafting questionnaire developed by Dianne A. Vella-Brodrick and Gavin R. Slemp focused on the three aspects of job crafting: cognitive, relational, and task crafting. JCQ is a 15 item, 7-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 7 (strongly agree). Items 5 through 10 show cognitive crafting, items 11 through 15 show relational crafting, while items 1 through 5 show task-crafting. Additionally, this scale demonstrated strong internal consistency, with Cronbach's alphas for WSPA and WSNA of .92 and .93, respectively.

Procedure

The study used a quantitative method with a correlational research design to investigate the relationship between the variables. To investigate the relationship between the variables, a convenience sampling strategy was applied. To enable researchers to formulate predictions based on the correlations found, the study also sought to examine the direction and strength of the association between these factors.

A sample of three hundred working adults from different organizations in Islamabad participated in the study. First and foremost, the organization's approval was attained. The data was gathered with the participants' consent. They were informed of the study's goal. Additionally, they were informed about their freedom to decline and exit at any time. Instructions on how to fill out the questionnaire were given to the participants. Additionally, participants were informed that they could ask any questions they had without holding back. The participants were likely to provide the proper response if they were given any questions pertaining to the topic. They were assured that any information they submitted would be kept confidential and used only for research. The demographic data, which included information on age, gender, marital status, occupation, and educational background, was also collected in conjunction with the questionnaire. Every additional ethical rule supplied by the American Psychological Association was adhered to. At the conclusion of the data collection, each participant received a thank-you for their participation. After all the data was gathered, it was loaded into SPSS-21 and JASP-19 for additional analysis and conclusion.

Statistical analysis

IBM SPSS Statistics, version 28.0.1.0, was utilized to conduct statistical analyses in a step-by-step manner. Prior to obtaining measures for central tendency and distribution, standardized (Z) scores were computed to check research variables for outliers. Second, to examine differences between male and female participants, independent sample tests were

conducted. Regression analysis was conducted to predict job crafting among working adults.

Results

Preliminary results

Table 2: Multiple Regression Analysis of Predictors of Task crafting (N=300)

Predictor						95% CI	
	b	SE	β	t	p	LL	UL
(Constant)	26.807	.947		28.299	.000	24.943	28.672
Narcissism	.071	.050	.084	1.418	.157	-.079	.115
Machiavellianism	-.350	.086	-.269	-4.086	.000	-.412	-.122
Psychopathy	.088	.066	.085	1.331	.184	-.147	.090
R	.234 ^a						
R ²	.055						
ΔR^2	.045						
F	5.711						

Note. *p < .05, ** p < .01, ***p < .001

Narcissism ($\beta = .084$, $p = .157$) does not predict task crafting. Machiavellianism ($\beta = -.269$, $p = .000$)

significantly predicts task crafting. Psychopathy ($\beta = .085$, $p = .184$) does not predict task crafting.

Table 3: Multiple Regression Analysis of Predictors of Cognitive Crafting (N=300)

Predictor						95% CI	
	b	SE	β	t	p	LL	UL
(Constant)	28.251	.906		31.183	.000	26.468	30.034
Narcissism	.088	.048	.106	1.826	.069	-.007	.182
Machiavellianism	-.410	.082	-.323	-5.003	.000	-.571	-.248
Psychopathy	.017	.064	.017	.268	.789	-.108	.142
R	.303 ^a						
R ²	.092						
ΔR^2	.083						
F	9.984						

Note. *p < .05, ** p < .01, ***p < .001

Narcissism ($\beta = .106$, $p = .069$), does not predict cognitive crafting. Machiavellianism ($\beta = -.323$, $p = .000$), significantly predicts cognitive crafting.

Psychopathy ($\beta = .017$, $p = .789$), does not predict cognitive crafting.

Table 4: Multiple Regression Analysis of Predictors of Relational Crafting (N=300)

Predictor						95% CI	
	b	SE	β	t	p	LL	UL
(Constant)	25.721	1.038		24.779	.000	23.679	27.764
Narcissism	.083	.055	.090	1.504	.134	-.026	.191
Machiavellianism	-.088	.094	-.063	-.943	.346	-.273	.096
Psychopathy	-.129	.073	-.115	-1.766	.078	-.272	.015

R	.160 ^a					
R ²	.026					
ΔR ²	.016					
F	2.584					

Note. *p < .05, ** p < .01, ***p < .001

Narcissism (β = .090, p = .134), does not predict relational crafting. Machiavellianism (β = -.063, p = .346), does not significantly predict relational crafting.

Psychopathy (β = -.115, p = .078), does not predict relational crafting.

Table 5: Mean Differences in Predictor and Outcome Variable of Participants' Gender (N=300)

Variables	Male (n=183)		Female (n=117)		t	p
	M	SD	M	SD		
Narcissism	14.71	7.097	15.09	6.212	-.474	.636
Machiavellianism	7.66	4.229	8.66	4.696	-1.908	.057
Psychopathy	9.62	5.368	10.83	5.767	-1.853	.065
Job Crafting	133.01	24.265	124.49	25.313	2.913	.004

Note. *p < .05, ** p < .01, ***p < .001, JC–Job crafting, MAW–Motivation at work

Table 5 shows the evidence of significant difference among male (M = 133.01, SD = 24.265) and female (M = 124.49, SD = 25.313) in job crafting (p = 0.004), reporting higher levels of job crafting in males than females. However, there is no significant difference in Narcissism (p = .636), Machiavellianism (p = .057), and psychopathy (p = .065) across both genders.

Discussion

One of the key findings of this study is that participants who have Machiavellian personality traits are supposed to be better at job crafting than people possessing narcissistic and psychopathy traits. In *The Prince* (1513/1981), Machiavelli suggested that rulers, able to ignore their ethics and values, would be more successful than those who rule truthfully and honestly. In the present day, individuals who demonstrate a lack of concern for conventional morality, are emotionally detached, and tend to manipulate others are said to have high levels of personality trait Machiavellianism (Christie & Geis, 1970). The study of Machiavellianism proliferated in the 1970s after initial studies by Christie and Geis (1970: 312) yielded a personality construct with three dimensions: (a) endorsement of deception and manipulation, (b) a cynical perspective on human nature, and (c) a disregard for conventional morality. Christie and Geis concluded from their studies that

high Machs (employees with high levels of Machiavellianism) “manipulate more, win more, are persuaded less, persuade others more, and otherwise differ significantly from their low Machiavellian counterparts.” Subsequent research has isolated important differences between high Machs and low Machs— (individuals with low levels of Machiavellianism). For example, high Machs tend to have higher levels of mistrust, cynicism, egocentricity, and propensity for interpersonal manipulation (McHoskey, 1999), as well as interpersonal coldness (Wiggins & Broughton, 1985), narcissism (McHoskey, 1995), anxiety (Fehr, Samsom, & Paulhus, 1992), and external locus of control (Mudrack, 1990).

In the field of management, scholars’ interest in Machiavellianism originated from its alleged relationship with work performance. In line with Machiavelli’s reasoning and the findings of early Machiavellianism research, scholars have hypothesized that—compared to low Machs—employees with high levels of Machiavellianism should exhibit higher levels of performance at work because they tend to manipulate (Christie & Geis, 1970; Wilson, Near, & Miller, 1996), lack empathy (Paal & Bereczkei, 2007), prefer opportunism to cooperation (Sakalaki, Richardson, & Thepaut, 2007), engage in revenge-seeking behavior (Meyer,

1992), and are less likely to reciprocate favors (Meyer, 1992). Yet three decades of research have yielded inconclusive results, with some studies showing Machiavellianism to be positively related to work outcomes (Dahling, Whitaker, & Levy, 2009; Turner & Martinez, 1977), others demonstrating a negative relationship (Gable & Topol, 1988; Topol & Gable, 1990), and a third set of studies reporting no relationship at all (Gable & Topol, 1991; Gemmill & Heisler, 1972; Hunt & Chonko, 1984).

Despite their attitude (Gunnthorsdottir et al., 2002; Rauthmann, 2012), compared to psychopaths and narcissists, Machiavellians are highly pragmatic and rational leaders without a great vision (Bedell et al., 2006; Christie and Geis, 1970; Glad, 2002). Their strategic long-term planning builds on agentic motives (e.g., power, money) and self-beneficial goal pursuit (Diehl et al., 2006; Elias, 2013; Fehr et al., 1992; Jones and Paulhus, 2009; Rauthmann and Will, 2011). These behavioral tendencies corroborate creativity, experimentation, and opportunity seeking. Thus, Machiavellians are less likely to venture into the unknown. Their quest for unmitigated achievement and winning at any cost supports this (Ryckman et al., 1994). Further, their high result orientation only serves the accomplishment of their personal goals (Fehr et al., 1992). Zettler et al. (2011) demonstrate that Machiavellianism positively relates to self-related career commitment and negatively to organizational, supervisor, and team commitment. Machiavellianism is positively associated with choosing financial success as a primary business goal (McHoskey, 1995). Aziz et al. (2002) find that Machiavellian tendencies allow higher sales performance. Yet, Machiavellians are destructive leaders: they manipulate, lie, exploit others, and focus exclusively on their own goals (Spain et al., 2014).

Our study suggests that individuals high in Machiavellianism engage in more job crafting than those with high levels of narcissism or psychopathy. One possible explanation for this is that Machiavellians prioritize their own interests and financial gain over the organization's goals. As a result, they often engage in behaviors like backstabbing, using others as leverage to advance their careers, and even undermining colleagues for personal gain (LeBreton et al., 2018).

Highly motivated by self-interest, they are less concerned with the welfare of others. In this study it is evident that when examining job crafting, Machiavellianism significantly predicts task crafting and contextual crafting, but not relational crafting. One reason to explain this is because Machiavellians tend to disregard their colleagues and relationships, viewing them merely as tools for personal advancement. Their detached approach to interpersonal interactions emphasizes self-interest over relational concerns. McHoskey's (1999) research, conducted with college students, supports this view, finding that Machiavellians are driven more by extrinsic goals, such as financial success, than by intrinsic goals like community engagement. He also found a negative relationship between Machiavellianism and social interest, which reflects care and concern for others.

The results of this study indicate job crafting is not predicted by narcissism. While direct research on narcissism's impact on job crafting is limited, existing studies suggest that narcissistic individuals may not excel in this area. Narcissists often prioritize self-promotion and may engage in manipulative behaviors to advance their interests. For instance, research indicates that narcissism is linked to self-serving biases in the workplace, where individuals attribute their successes to personal factors and failures to external circumstances. Additionally, narcissistic CEOs have been observed to engage in risky and opportunistic behaviors, such as insider trading, which can negatively impact organizational performance (Jiang et al., 2025). A study found that narcissist CEOs tend to overestimate their access to non-public information and display a careless attitude toward legal consequences, leading to poorer financial outcomes (Jiang et al., 2025).

These tendencies suggest that narcissistic individuals may focus more on self-interest and less on collaborative efforts, potentially hindering their effectiveness in job crafting, which often requires adaptability and consideration of others' perspectives. Now, if we dig deeper into the dark triad personality qualities. These individuals are all focused on their own objectives. They will use every resource at their disposal to achieve their goals. However, why did participants with narcissistic and psychopathic qualities score lower on job crafting than

Machiavellian individuals? Are Machiavellians doing well than narcissists and psychopaths in their professions? Or do they tend to redesign their jobs because they have special skills like intelligence, or any other qualities? Or is it anything to do with the culture where they are brought up and they are taught in a way that they can do anything to get what they want, since this research is quite different from the research done in western cultures. Machiavellianism's development appears to be largely influenced by the environment, with only modest genetic inheritance (Vernon, Villani, Vickers, & Harris, 2008; Veselka, Schermer, & Vernon, 2011). Machiavellian views and tactics are likely learnt socially and reinforced through direct modelling of attachment figures (Kraut & Price, 1976) in combination with traumatic, harsh, and neglectful environments (Láng & Birkás, 2014; Láng & Lénárd, 2015; McIlwain, 2011). To conclude this point, it is necessary for future researchers to identify dark triad personalities in different cultures and what significantly motivates them in their lives, personally and professionally both. Specially in Pakistan this side of the personality should be addressed with respect to culture, intelligence, and other motivation factors.

T test was performed to account for any significant difference across gender of the sample. Results revealed significant difference among male and female in job crafting, reporting higher levels of job crafting in males than females. However, there is no significant difference in Narcissism, Machiavellianism and psychopathy across both genders. Similarly, research on job crafting has yielded conflicting findings. Job crafting is more common among women, according to certain studies (Slemp & Vella-Brodrick, 2014; Rudolph et al., 2017) whereas it is more common among men, according to other studies (Petrou et al., 2017).

Implications

The findings of this study have significant implications for organizations, businesses, and mental health practitioners. Firstly, this research provides valuable insights for organizations to better understand their employees with Dark Triad personality traits, namely Machiavellianism, Narcissism, and Psychopathy. By recognizing the characteristics and tendencies of these individuals, organizations can develop more effective hiring

processes, screening for these traits in the early stages of recruitment.

Moreover, this study's results can inform the development of interventions aimed at enhancing the job performance and job crafting abilities of employees with Dark Triad traits. By acknowledging the strengths and weaknesses of these individuals, organizations can create tailored training programs and coaching strategies to help them excel in their roles.

The findings of this study also challenge the conventional wisdom that Machiavellian individuals are inherently detrimental to organizational success. On the contrary, this research suggests that Machiavellians can be valuable assets to organizations, as their success is directly tied to the organization's success.

Furthermore, this study's implications extend to the field of psychology and mental health. The results provide a foundation for psychologists and mental health practitioners to better understand and support individuals with Dark Triad traits. By acknowledging the strengths and weaknesses of these individuals, practitioners can develop more effective therapeutic strategies to help them navigate their personal and professional lives.

Ultimately, this study's findings underscore the importance of considering the cultural and contextual factors that influence the expression and impact of Dark Triad personality traits. By doing so, organizations, businesses, and mental health practitioners can work together to create more effective support systems and interventions that promote the well-being and success of individuals with these traits.

This study highlights the importance of considering cultural nuances when assessing the impact of personality traits on job performance. To advance our understanding of Dark Triad traits, future research should explore each trait independently, employing diverse methodologies and incorporating a broader range of variables. Potential avenues include examining relationships between Dark Triad traits and cultural factors, socio-economic status, leadership styles, parenting styles, and organizational outcomes. Additionally, qualitative methods can provide a deeper understanding of Machiavellian individuals' motivations and behaviors. Future studies should also

investigate the consequences of promoting Machiavellianism in the workplace, including its impact on employee well-being and organizational citizenship behavior. Moreover, researchers should explore the motivational factors driving Machiavellians' job crafting, as well as the relationship between Dark Triad traits and leadership styles. By addressing these gaps, researchers and practitioners can develop more effective strategies for managing and developing employees in the Pakistani context, ultimately creating more effective talent management systems that cater to unique employee needs and characteristics.

Limitations

This study has three primary limitations. Firstly, the diverse sample composition, spanning various sectors and hierarchical levels, may have obscured nuanced differences that could have emerged from a more targeted approach. Specifically, the sample included individuals from disparate levels, such as low-level employees, supervisors, leaders, and workers. This heterogeneity, while providing a broad perspective, may have diluted the findings. A more focused study concentrating on a specific group, such as leaders, supervisors, or low-level managers, could have yielded more precise information and deeper insights into the dynamics within that context.

Secondly, the brevity of the Dark Triad personality scale, with only four questions per subscale, may have restricted the depth of information captured for each trait. Employing a more comprehensive scale could have provided richer insights and more accurate results.

Thirdly, the geographical constraint of the sample, limited to Islamabad's population, undermines the generalizability of the findings to other regions of Pakistan. A more diverse sample, representative of various areas across Pakistan, would have enhanced the study's external validity and provided a more comprehensive understanding of the relationships between Dark Triad traits, motivation, and job outcomes within the Pakistani context.

Conclusion

This quantitative study investigated the role of Dark Triad personality traits, comprising Narcissism, Machiavellianism, and Psychopathy, in influencing

job crafting of employees. Using a cross-sectional approach, the study employed regression, mediation, and correlational analyses to examine the relationships between these variables. The results revealed that Machiavellianism was a significant predictor of job crafting. In contrast, Narcissism did not significantly predict job crafting nor did psychopathy. Notably, Machiavellianism emerged as the most influential trait, predicting both job crafting and motivation. Moreover, gender did not have any significant influence over these traits, but gender was a significant predictor of motivation, and job crafting. These findings suggest that Machiavellianism plays a crucial role in shaping employee behavior and outcomes, highlighting the importance of considering this trait in organizational settings. Overall, this study contributes to our understanding of the complex relationships between Dark Triad traits, motivation, and job outcomes such as job crafting, providing valuable insights for researchers and practitioners alike.

Declaration

Strict adherence to ethical standards was maintained, including obtaining permission from the SZABIST Human Research and Ethics Committee and the Department of Psychology. Informed permission was acquired to ensure that participants were aware of the study's purpose, risks, and benefits prior to voluntarily agreeing to take part. This highlighted the independence of the participants. Data security, participant privacy and confidentiality, and debriefing sessions as described in the ethical considerations section were all guaranteed.

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